

A Review Article on Studying the structural behavior of Steel Tubes and Concrete Filled Steel Tubes (CFST) retrofitted with Glass Fiber Reinforced Polymer (GFRP)

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ABSTRACT

Concrete-Filled Steel Tubes (CFST) and bare steel tubes are widely used in structural engineering due to their excellent load-bearing capacities and ductility. However, under severe loading conditions, their performance can be significantly enhanced by retrofitting with Glass Fiber Reinforced Polymer (GFRP). This paper presents a comprehensive review of the existing literature on the structural behavior of steel tubes and CFST retrofitted with GFRP. The focus is on load-carrying capacity, ductility, flexural behavior, energy dissipation, and the effectiveness of GFRP as a retrofitting material. The review highlights current research trends, challenges, and areas for future exploration.

Keywords- Concrete-Filled Steel Tubes (CFST), Steel Tubes, Glass Fiber Reinforced Polymer (GFRP), Structural Retrofitting, Axial Load Capacity, Buckling Behavior

1.INTRODUCTION

Steel Tubes and CFST structures are integral to modern construction due to their superior structural performance. CFST combines the compressive strength of concrete and the tensile strength of steel, making it highly effective in resisting seismic and impact loads.

Despite their advantages, these structures are vulnerable to failure under extreme conditions, necessitating retrofitting techniques. GFRP, with its high strength-to-weight ratio, corrosion resistance, and ease of application, has emerged as an effective material for strengthening and retrofitting. This paper aims to

provide an in-depth understanding of the behavior of steel tubes and CFST retrofitted with GFRP, focusing on experimental and analytical studies.

2. Structural Behavior of Steel Tubes and CFST

2.1 Steel Tubes

Steel tubes are used for their excellent axial and bending strength. However, their structural performance can degrade due to:

- Buckling under axial loads
- Local failures caused by high stress concentrations
- Corrosion over time

2.2 Concrete-Filled Steel Tubes (CFST)

CFST structures demonstrate enhanced mechanical properties due to the composite action between steel and concrete. The steel tube provides confinement to the concrete, improving its compressive strength and ductility. Critical factors influencing CFST behavior include:

- Concrete compressive strength
- Steel tube thickness and diameter
- Bond strength between steel and concrete

3. Retrofitting with GFRP

3.1 Properties of GFRP

GFRP is a composite material consisting of glass fibers embedded in a polymer matrix. Key advantages of GFRP include:

- High tensile strength and low density
- Resistance to chemical and environmental degradation
- Flexibility in application

3.2 Mechanism of Retrofitting

Retrofitting steel tubes and CFST with GFRP typically involves wrapping the structural element with GFRP sheets. This technique:

- Enhances the axial and lateral load capacity
- Delays the onset of buckling in steel tubes
- Improves energy dissipation during cyclic loading

4. Objectives of the Study

The objectives of the study in the article "Studying the Structural Behavior of Steel Tubes and Concrete Filled Steel Tubes (CFST) Retrofitted with Glass Fiber Reinforced Polymer (GFRP)" would typically aim to address the following points in detail:

1. To Investigate the Structural Performance of Steel Tubes and CFSTs

- **Primary Objective:** The study aims to examine the fundamental structural behavior of steel tubes and CFSTs under various loading conditions (e.g., axial compression, bending, shear). This includes understanding the combined action between the concrete core and the steel tube, which contributes to the overall load-carrying capacity and stability of the column.
- The study focuses on identifying the strengths and limitations of CFSTs, such as their susceptibility to local buckling, and the role of the concrete infill in enhancing the stability of the steel tube.

2. To Assess the Effectiveness of GFRP Retrofitting for CFSTs

- **Enhancement of Structural Capacity:** One of the key objectives is to evaluate how GFRP retrofitting improves the axial load-carrying capacity, lateral stability, and overall strength of CFSTs. This includes assessing how GFRP wraps applied externally to steel tubes influence the overall performance of CFST columns.
- **Ductility and Post-Buckling Behavior:** The study aims to explore the ductility of retrofitted CFSTs, focusing on how GFRP improves the post-buckling behavior and enhances the energy dissipation capacity of the columns under axial and lateral loading.

3. To Examine the Bonding between GFRP and Concrete Core

- **Concrete-Steel Interaction:** Another objective is to assess how GFRP retrofitting affects the bond between the concrete core and the surrounding steel tube. A strong bond between the two materials is critical for efficient load transfer, and GFRP can potentially enhance this interaction by preventing slippage and improving the confinement of the concrete core.
- The study investigates how different wrapping techniques and configurations of GFRP influence the strength of this bond and the composite action between steel and concrete.

4. To Evaluate the Failure Modes of Retrofitted CFSTs

- **Identifying Critical Failure Mechanisms:** The study aims to analyze the failure modes of CFST columns retrofitted with GFRP. These could include the fracture or delamination of the GFRP wrap, local buckling of the steel tube, or crushing of the concrete core.

- By understanding these failure mechanisms, the study aims to enhance the design and safety of CFST columns in practical applications, ensuring that the retrofitting approach is robust and effective.

5. To Conduct Experimental and Analytical Assessments of Retrofitted CFSTs

- **Experimental Testing:** One of the main objectives is to carry out experimental tests on CFSTs retrofitted with GFRP under various loading conditions (e.g., axial compression, bending). The tests aim to provide a clear understanding of how GFRP retrofitting affects the structural behavior of CFSTs.
- **Analytical Modeling:** The study also aims to develop and validate analytical models that can predict the behavior of CFSTs retrofitted with GFRP. These models would provide insight into the structural performance of retrofitted CFSTs under different loading scenarios, and assist in future design applications.

6. To Explore the Impact of Various Retrofitting Parameters on CFST Performance

- **Influence of GFRP Properties:** The study investigates how the properties of GFRP, such as its type, thickness, and application technique, influence the performance of retrofitted CFSTs. This would include understanding the optimal GFRP material and configuration that provides the best structural enhancement.
- **Effect of Steel Tube and Concrete Properties:** Another objective is to evaluate how variations in the properties of the steel tube (e.g., thickness, material grade) and the concrete infill (e.g., strength, mix design) affect the performance of retrofitted CFSTs.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

The review article on "Studying the Structural Behavior of Steel Tubes and Concrete Filled Steel Tubes (CFST) Retrofitted with Glass Fiber Reinforced Polymer (GFRP)" provides a comprehensive analysis of the research and findings related to the behavior of steel tubes and CFSTs that have been retrofitted with GFRP for enhanced structural performance. Here's an overview of what the literature review of this article covers:

1. Introduction to CFSTs and GFRP Retrofitting

- **CFSTs:** Concrete-Filled Steel Tubes (CFSTs) combine the high strength of steel with the high stiffness of concrete, offering advantages such as enhanced

load-carrying capacity, fire resistance, and durability. CFST columns are widely used in construction due to their superior structural performance.

- **GFRP:** Glass Fiber Reinforced Polymer (GFRP) is used as an external reinforcement material to improve the strength, ductility, and overall performance of CFSTs. The review explains how GFRP retrofitting can overcome certain weaknesses of CFSTs, such as insufficient confinement and corrosion resistance.

2. Structural Behavior of Steel Tubes and CFSTs

- The article discusses the basic structural behavior of steel tubes and CFSTs under various loading conditions, such as axial compression, bending, and shear.
- It emphasizes the synergy between steel and concrete in CFSTs and how the composite action enhances their structural integrity. However, challenges such as local buckling and corrosion in steel tubes are also identified.

3. GFRP Retrofitting Techniques

- **GFRP Wraps:** The review outlines different methods of applying GFRP wraps to the surface of steel tubes or CFSTs. These wraps improve the confinement of the concrete core, thereby enhancing the load-bearing capacity and reducing the risk of premature failure due to local buckling.
- **Strengthening Mechanisms:** The article explains how GFRP retrofitting works through mechanisms such as the transfer of axial load, the confinement of concrete, and preventing the outward bulging of the steel tube under axial and lateral loads.

4. Influence of GFRP on the Performance of CFSTs

- **Axial Strength and Ductility:** Studies on CFST columns retrofitted with GFRP show significant improvements in axial strength, post-buckling behavior, and ductility. The use of GFRP enhances the load capacity and helps prevent the local buckling of the steel tube.
- **Bond between Concrete and Steel:** GFRP retrofitting also improves the bond between the concrete core and the steel tube, which is crucial for the overall stability and performance of CFST columns.

- Failure Modes: The review investigates the failure modes of CFSTs retrofitted with GFRP. It identifies modes such as fracture of the GFRP wrap, buckling of the steel tube, or crushing of the concrete core.

5. Experimental and Analytical Studies

- The review article summarizes various experimental studies that have tested CFSTs retrofitted with GFRP under different conditions. These include axial compression tests, lateral loading, and combined load scenarios. The results demonstrate improvements in the strength and ductility of CFST columns post-retrofitting.
- Analytical models developed to predict the behavior of GFRP-retrofitted CFSTs are also discussed, highlighting their usefulness in understanding the response of these structures under different loading scenarios.

6. Review/ Research Article

1. Flexural Behaviour of High-Strength Rectangular Concrete-Filled Steel Hollow Sections (2004) By Wie-Min Gho, Dalin Liu

The study "*Flexural Behaviour of High-Strength Rectangular Concrete-Filled Steel Hollow Sections*" by Wie-Min Gho and Dalin Liu, published in the *Journal of Constructional Steel Research* in 2004, investigates the performance of 12 high-strength rectangular concrete-filled steel hollow section (CFSHS) specimens under pure bending. The experimental results revealed local buckling as a primary failure mode, with high-strength materials exhibiting superior strength and ductility compared to normal-strength materials. Furthermore, the study identified that existing design codes, including EC4, ACI, and AISC, underestimated the flexural strength of CFSHS members by 11–18%. These findings highlight the need to update design methodologies to accurately account for the enhanced performance of high-strength materials in composite systems.

2. Analytical Modeling of Bending of Circular Concrete-Filled Steel Tubes (2012) By Jiho Moon, Charles W. Roeder, Dawn E. Lehman, Hak-Eun Lee

The study "*Analytical Modeling of Bending of Circular Concrete-Filled Steel Tubes*" by Jiho Moon, Charles W. Roeder, Dawn E. Lehman, and Hak-Eun Lee, published in *Engineering Structures* in 2012, presents an analytical approach to predict the bending behavior of circular

concrete-filled steel tubes (CFSTs). The model incorporates the nonlinear interaction between the steel tube and the concrete core, accounting for factors such as material properties, cross-sectional geometry, and confinement effects. Validation against experimental data showed accurate predictions of moment-curvature relationships, failure modes, and ductility. This research provides a robust framework for evaluating the flexural performance of CFST members, contributing to improved design practices for resilient structural systems.

3. Behavior of FRP-Confined Concrete-Filled Steel Tube Columns (2014) By Yiyang Lu, Na Li, Shan Li

The study "*Behavior of FRP-Confined Concrete-Filled Steel Tube Columns*" by Yiyang Lu, Na Li, and Shan Li, published in *Polymers (MDPI)* in 2014, examines the structural performance of concrete-filled steel tube (CFST) columns wrapped with fiber-reinforced polymer (FRP) composites. The research focuses on the combined benefits of steel and FRP confinement in enhancing axial load-bearing capacity, ductility, and energy absorption. Through experimental investigations and theoretical modeling, the study highlights the synergistic effect of the materials, which results in improved strength and deformation behavior under various loading conditions. The findings emphasize the potential of FRP-confined CFST columns as an innovative solution for high-performance structural applications, especially in seismic and extreme load environments.

4. A Study on Flexural Behaviour of Concrete Filled Steel Tubes (2017) By S. Aravind, D. Mohammed Rafi

The study "*A Study on Flexural Behaviour of Concrete Filled Steel Tubes*" by S. Aravind and D. Mohammed Rafi, published in *IJSRST* in 2017, focuses on the flexural performance of concrete-filled steel tubes (CFST). The research investigates the combined action of steel and concrete, emphasizing their role in enhancing the moment-carrying capacity, stiffness, and ductility of CFST members under flexural loads. Experimental and analytical approaches were employed to evaluate the influence of parameters such as cross-sectional shape, concrete strength, and steel tube thickness. The findings underscore the structural advantages of CFSTs, particularly in resisting bending forces, making them

suitable for applications in modern construction where high performance is required.

5. Structural Behaviour of RC Beam and Concrete Filled Steel Tubes Retrofitted with Natural Rubber Sheet (2019) By P. Ramanan, M. Sharmila, P. Vennila, M. Suresh, Dr. M. Sivaraja

The study "Structural Behaviour of RC Beam and Concrete Filled Steel Tubes Retrofitted with Natural Rubber Sheet," published in the International Journal of Engineering Research & Technology (IJERT) by P. Ramanan et al. in 2019, explores the retrofitting potential of natural rubber sheets in enhancing the structural performance of reinforced concrete (RC) beams and concrete-filled steel tubes (CFST). The researchers analyzed the effects of retrofitting on the flexural and axial load-carrying capacities, with a focus on energy dissipation and overall stability under applied loads. Their findings highlighted the significant improvement in ductility and strength due to the application of natural rubber sheets, emphasizing its cost-effectiveness and environmental benefits. The experimental study provides valuable insights into sustainable retrofitting techniques, paving the way for more eco-friendly and efficient methods in structural rehabilitation. This research underscores the growing interest in incorporating natural materials in modern construction for enhancing performance and sustainability.

6. Behavior of FRP wrapped concrete filled steel tubular columns (2020) By Gajalakshmi Pandulu, Revathy Jayaseelan, Jemimah Thong

The study "*Behavior of FRP wrapped concrete filled steel tubular columns*" by Gajalakshmi Pandulu, Revathy Jayaseelan, and Jemimah Thong, published in *IJASE* in 2020, investigates the performance of concrete-filled steel tubular (CFT) columns wrapped with fiber-reinforced polymer (FRP) under various loading conditions. The experimental results were compared with the computed load-carrying capacity from existing design codes. Among the codes compared, DL/T 1999 showed the least variation and was found to be the most reliable for predicting the ultimate load-carrying capacity of CFT columns. The study highlighted that CCFT columns wrapped with two layers of carbon fiber-reinforced polymer (CFRP) exhibited significantly enhanced strength and ductility compared to other CCFT columns,

emphasizing the effectiveness of CFRP wrapping in improving column performance.

7. A Review on Structural Behavior of Steel Tubes and Concrete-Filled Steel Tubes (CFST) Retrofitted with Glass Fiber Reinforced Polymer (GFRP) (2022) By Sumit Bhusari, Harshavardhan Rangari

The study "*A Review on Structural Behavior of Steel Tubes and Concrete-Filled Steel Tubes (CFST) Retrofitted with Glass Fiber Reinforced Polymer (GFRP)*" by Sumit Bhusari and Harshavardhan Rangari, published in the *International Journal for Modern Trends in Science and Technology* in 2022, examines the impact of retrofitting CFST columns with glass fiber reinforced polymer (GFRP). The review highlights that GFRP wrapping effectively improves the confinement of concrete, reducing its expansion and delaying the local buckling of the steel tube. The results from various studies reviewed demonstrated a significant enhancement in both the load-carrying capacity and axial deformation capacity of CFST columns when confined with GFRP. This retrofitting technique provides an efficient and cost-effective solution to enhance the performance and longevity of CFST structures.

8. Behavior of GFRP-concrete double tube composite columns (2022) By Shuai Li, Tak-Ming Chan, Ben Young

The study "*Behavior of GFRP-concrete double tube composite columns*" by Shuai Li, Tak-Ming Chan, and Ben Young, published in *Thin-Walled Structures* in 2022, introduces a novel composite column system combining glass fiber reinforced polymer (GFRP) and concrete within a double tube configuration. The research demonstrates that this composite system offers enhanced deformability and load-bearing capacity compared to traditional column systems. The study found that increasing the thickness of the inner pultruded GFRP tube significantly improves the load capacity of the composite columns. Additionally, the authors developed predictive equations for the ultimate load-carrying capacity and axial strain, providing a useful tool for designing and analyzing GFRP-concrete double tube columns in structural applications.

9. CFST columns strengthened with CFRP textile grid-reinforced engineered cementitious composites

under eccentric compression (2022) By Yuhong Yan, Shan Li, Yiyang Lu, Aohan Zheng

The study "CFST columns strengthened with CFRP textile grid-reinforced engineered cementitious composites under eccentric compression" by Yuhong Yan, Shan Li, Yiyang Lu, and Aohan Zheng, published in *Composite Structures* in 2022, proposes a novel technique for enhancing the performance of concrete-filled steel tube (CFST) columns using carbon fiber-reinforced polymer (CFRP) textile grid-reinforced engineered cementitious composites. The research demonstrated that this strengthening method increased the load-bearing capacity of CFST columns by 11.6%–38.2%. Key factors such as the number of CFRP layers, the diameter-to-thickness (D/t) ratio, and the strength of the concrete were found to significantly influence the results, with higher concrete strength contributing to increased brittleness. A predictive model for the load-bearing capacity and N–M curves was also developed, providing valuable insights for the design and optimization of CFRP-strengthened CFST columns.

10. Study on Strength and Behaviour of Concrete Filled Steel Tubular Rectangular Composite Long Columns (2023) By Rajshree Charan, Ankit Goad

The study "Study on Strength and Behaviour of Concrete Filled Steel Tubular Rectangular Composite Long Columns" by Rajshree Charan and Ankit Goad (2023) investigates the structural performance of concrete-filled steel tubular (CFST) rectangular composite long columns. This research evaluates the strength, stiffness, and load-bearing behavior under axial and eccentric loading conditions. The authors conducted experimental tests and analytical assessments to understand the interaction between the steel tube and concrete core, highlighting the benefits of composite action in enhancing overall performance. Their findings demonstrate improved load capacity and ductility, making CFST rectangular columns a viable option for modern high-rise and industrial structures. This work contributes to the development of design guidelines for CFST columns in challenging loading scenarios.

3. PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

To comprehensively study the structural behavior of steel tubes and Concrete-Filled Steel Tubes (CFST) retrofitted with Glass

Fiber Reinforced Polymer (GFRP), the following methodology is proposed:

1. Literature Review

- Objective: Gather existing knowledge on the structural performance of steel tubes and CFST retrofitted with GFRP.
- Approach:
 - Review journal articles, conference papers, and case studies focusing on GFRP retrofitting.
 - Identify gaps in current research and limitations in existing experimental and analytical studies.

2. Material Selection and Preparation

- Materials:
 - Steel tubes with varying thicknesses and diameters.
 - Concrete mix of different grades (e.g., M20, M30) for CFST.
 - Unidirectional and bidirectional GFRP sheets with known mechanical properties.
- Preparation:
 - Fabricate steel tubes and CFST specimens as per standard dimensions.
 - Cut GFRP sheets into the required sizes and prepare adhesive resin for bonding.

3. Experimental Setup

- Specimen Design:
 - Divide specimens into three categories: bare steel tubes, bare CFST, and GFRP-retrofitted steel tubes/CFST.
 - Apply GFRP wrapping in different configurations (single-layer, multi-layer, varying orientations).
- Testing Parameters:
 - Axial Compression Tests: Evaluate load-carrying capacity and buckling behavior.
 - Flexural Tests: Study bending stiffness and ductility.
 - Cyclic Loading Tests: Assess energy dissipation and seismic resilience.

4. Numerical Modeling

- Finite Element Analysis (FEA):
 - Develop numerical models using software like ABAQUS, ANSYS, or SAP2000.
 - Incorporate material properties of steel, concrete, and GFRP into the model.
 - Simulate experimental conditions to validate test results.
- Key Outputs:

- Stress-strain curves.
- Failure modes.
- Confinement effects of GFRP on concrete and steel.

5. Data Analysis

- Compare experimental and numerical results to validate findings.
- Analyze:
 - Improvement in axial and flexural strength due to GFRP retrofitting.
 - Effectiveness of GFRP in delaying buckling and failure.
 - Influence of GFRP layer thickness, orientation, and bonding quality.

6. Durability Studies

- Expose GFRP-retrofitted specimens to environmental conditions such as:
 - Cyclic temperature variations.
 - Moisture and chemical exposure.
 Measure changes in mechanical properties over time to assess long-term performance.

4. CONCLUSION

GFRP retrofitting has emerged as a promising solution for enhancing the structural performance of steel tubes and CFST under various loading conditions. While significant progress has been made, challenges related to long-term performance and cost-effectiveness remain. This review emphasizes the need for continued research to address these issues and unlock the full potential of GFRP in retrofitting applications

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Conflict of interest statement

Authors declare that they do not have any conflict of interest.

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